

MODERN METHODS FOR THE PREVENTION OF WEDGE-SHAPED DEFECT OF TEETH

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Abstract. Non-carious dental lesions are fairly common diseases that almost every dentist encounter during his work. Among them, one should single out a disease that manifests itself in the form of a special shaped defect in dental tissue. At the initial examination, it immediately catches the eye, as the defect takes on a wedge-shaped shape. Due to its appearance, this disease was called a wedge-shaped defect [1]. According to studies, every year there are more and more patients with this pathology. Many scientists attribute this to the improper use of hygiene products, and others to the excessive consumption of products containing acids. The prevalence of this defect increases with age, most often it is found in people older than 45 years [2]. This lesion violates the aesthetic appearance of a smile, and in addition, it can lead to increased sensitivity of the teeth [3]. Scientists have not come to a consensus about the causes of the disease and the methods of its treatment [4]. However, in many cases, the disease can be prevented by applying simple methods of prevention.

Keywords: wedge-shaped defect, defect of teeth, causes, prevention.

Introduction. Every person dream of a beautiful smile, but most people have various dental diseases. Currently, the number of patients with non-carious lesions has increased significantly. One of them is a wedge-shaped defect of the teeth. This disease can be easily seen during a smile, since the teeth in the neck area acquire a wedge-shaped appearance. With this disease, the hard tissues of the teeth adjacent to the gum are damaged [5; 6; 7].

This defect is quite common, it is found in approximately 20-34% of the population.

According to statistics, this lesion is mainly diagnosed in people over 45 years old, presumably due to the possible presence of periodontal diseases at this age, but it can also manifest itself in young people [8; 9].

With a wedge-shaped defect, hypersensitivity gradually develops, which can further lead to tooth loss and concomitant diseases, such as gum inflammation. There are various methods of treating this disease, but they all

have their own difficulties [10]. The most effective way to combat this defect is to prevent its development, i.e., to follow the rules of prevention.

Materials and Methods. When writing the article, theoretical analysis and generalization of data from scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists on modern methods of preventing wedge-shaped defects of teeth were used.

Research results. There are several reasons for the occurrence of a wedge-shaped defect:

- chemical. Under the influence of acids contained in food and drinks, the structure of the enamel is damaged;
- physical and mechanical. The defect occurs due to malocclusion, since the load is not distributed correctly;
- mechanical. Enamel is damaged under the influence of abrasive pastes and hard toothbrushes [11; 12].

There are several ways to combat a wedge-shaped defect. However, it should be remembered that even with successful treatment, there is a risk of relapse if you do not follow all the doctor's recommendations.

Among the preventive measures, the following can be distinguished:

- use of properly selected oral hygiene products;
- regular visits to the dentist for preventive examination;
- correction of malocclusion. If necessary, consult an orthodontist.
- annual professional dental hygiene cleaning;
- limitation or complete refusal of foods and drinks containing large amounts of acids;
- timely treatment of concomitant diseases, such as those associated with the gastrointestinal tract [13].

Conclusion. Wedge-shaped defect is a disease in which a tooth defect is formed in the gingival area [14]. The occurrence of this lesion can be prevented by adhering to preventive measures [15]. Only their implementation and careful attitude to your health will prevent the development of not only this disease, but also many others.

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